

GLOBAL METAL PRICE INDEX AND SOLAR ACTIVITY (1992 - 2025): $R^2=1.0$ (GROWTH PHASE), $R^2=0.92$ (DECLINE PHASE)

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Abstract

This report uses a methodological approach developed by W. S. Jevons and A. L. Chizhevsky. Solar cycle years were numbered according to the order established in solar astrophysics, grouped, and compared with the arithmetic mean values of world metal price indices. The resulting models have coefficients of determination of 1.0 (the phase of increasing solar activity) and 0.92 (the phase of decreasing solar activity). The projected value of the world metal price index for 2026 is 115.65, and for 2027, 127.53.

Keywords:

Global Metal Price Index, solar activity, Wolf numbers, economic cycles

In his article “Solar-Commercial Cycles,” W. S. Jevons placed graphs of solar activity cycles (Wolf number cycles) and corn price cycles in Delhi over the period 1760–1810 one after the other [1, P.227], that is, he compared solar and economic activity.

A. L. Chizhevsky in his monograph “The Cosmic Pulse of Life: Earth in the Embrace of the Sun” in Chapter 4 “The Sun and Epidemics” in Fig. 33 constructed a diagram that depicts the average solar activity cycle over a hundred years (the Wolf number cycle) and the average cases of cholera in Russia for the years of the solar cycle for the period 1823–1923 [2, p. 201]. That is, he applied the method of superimposing eras.

In this study, the average Wolf numbers and the average arithmetic values of world metal price indices for 1992–2025 are compared on one diagram.

The annual mean Wolf numbers, the main indicator of solar activity (SA), were taken from the well-known astrophysical website for the determination, conservation, and distribution of the international sunspot number [3]. They are presented in column 2 of Table 1.

The ordinal numbers of years in column 3 of Table 1 are determined as follows. The first year in a SA cycle is considered to be the first year of its growth, that is, the increase in the Wolf number, which is presented in column 2. Subsequent years are numbered sequentially, and the last year in the cycle is considered to be the year of the SA minimum. Years of Wolf number minimums in Table 1 are highlighted in blue. Years of maximums are highlighted in red.

The Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis website provides statistical data on annual values of the global metal price index for the period 1992–2025 [4]. These are presented in column 4 of Table 1. The 2016 global metal price index was set to 100.

Table 1. Average annual Wolf numbers, ordinal numbers of years in the SA cycles and the global metal price index, 1992–2025

1. The years	2. Число Вольфа. Wolf numbers, 1990 - 2025 гг.	3. The serial number of the year in the cycle of solar activity	4. Global price of Metal index, 1992 - 2025
1992	133	6	47.88
1993	76.1	7	40.45
1994	44.9	8	47.18
1995	25.1	9	57.52
1996	11.6	10	50.94
1997	28.9	1	50.91
1998	88.3	2	41.03
1999	136.3	3	41.39
2000	173.9	4	47.93
2001	170.4	5	41.79
2002	163.6	6	41.33
2003	99.3	7	48.38
2004	65.3	8	67.23
2005	45.8	9	82.84
2006	24.7	10	130.10
2007	12.6	11	160.66
2008	4.2	12	144.28
2009	4.8	1	121.44
2010	24.9	2	185.84
2011	80.8	3	209.36
2012	84.5	4	172.10
2013	94	5	165.42

2014	113.3	6	145.27
2015	69.8	7	105.60
2016	39.8	8	100.00
2017	21.7	9	122.19
2018	7	10	130.29
2019	3.6	11	135.32
2020	8.8	1	140.01
2021	29.6	2	205.41
2022	83.2	3	193.90
2023	125.5	4	188.55
2024	154.6	5	184.95
2025	123.2	6	188.83
2026		7	

The statistical data in Table 1 were then grouped by the ordinal numbers of years in the SA cycles. Column 2 of Table 2 shows the number of years with a given ordinal number for the period 1992–2025.

Table 2. Grouping of data from Table 1 by ordinal numbers of years in solar activity cycles

1. The serial number of the year in the cycle of solar activity	2. The number of such years for the period 1992 - 2025	Arithmetic mean:		5. Relative to the previous year's index
		3. Wolf number, 1992 - 2025	4. Global price of Metal index, 1992 - 2025	
1	3	14.17	104.12	0.72
2	3	47.60	144.10	1.38
3	3	100.10	148.21	1.03
4	3	127.97	136.19	0.92
5	3	139.70	130.72	0.96
6	4	133.28	105.83	0.81
7	3	81.73	64.81	0.61
8	3	50.00	71.47	1.10
9	3	30.87	87.52	1.22
10	3	14.43	103.77	1.19
11	2	8.10	147.99	1.43
12	1	4.20	144.28	0.97
Total:	34			

Based on rows 1–5 (years of SA growth) and columns 3 and 4 of Table 2, Figure 1 is used to construct a diagram. The coefficient of determination in this diagram is 1.0 (a third-degree polynomial). Since the resulting p-value of 0.0387 is strictly less than the critical level of 0.05, the parabolic model is statistically significant at the 5% significance level.

Fig. 1. Years of Wolf number growth and global metal price index, 15-year observation period 1992–2025.

Based on rows 6–12 (years of SA decline) and columns 3 and 4 of Table 2, the following diagram is constructed in Fig. 2. The resulting value of $p = 0.0112$ is strictly less than the 0.05 level. This means that the cubic model for the declining branch of the solar cycle is highly significant.

The approximating functions in the diagrams in Figures 2 and 3 allow us to obtain metal price index forecasts based on the forecast Wolf number. The forecast Wolf number can be determined based on the current NASA forecast, which is presented in Figure 3.

Fig. 2. Years of decline in Wolf numbers and the global metal price index, 19 years of observations for 1992–2025, overlapping era method

Fig. 3. Forecast of the development of the current 25th cycle of solar activity.

The actual global metal price index for 2025 (year 6 of the current SA cycle) is 188.83. 2026 is year 7 of the current 25th SA cycle. The ratio of the average index for year 7 to that for year 6 is 0.61. Therefore, the forecast value of the index for 2026 is $188.83 * 0.61 = 115.65$.

Similarly, we determine that the predicted value of the index for 2027 is $115.65 * 1.10 = 127.53$.

I previously proposed calling the science that studies the relationship between solar and economic activity helioeconomics.

Events such as sanctions, wars, epidemics, and others can lead to inaccuracies in the developed forecast.

Reference

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